

SAMBAH Code File 5

ATag Data Analysis

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1 Introduction

This document (the `.Rnw` version) contains the R code to derive an estimate of p_c , the average probability of a porpoise emitting at least one click during time periods equal to those of the Kerteminde detection trial encounters. The document is based on SAMBAH internal reports; this version has been created to accompany the paper:

Amundin et al. In press. Estimating the abundance of the critically endangered Baltic Proper harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*) population using passive acoustic monitoring. *Ecology and Evolution*.

More information about the analysis is given in the methods section of the paper.

The final section is a preliminary analysis of diel patterns, made at the suggestion of a reviewer of the paper.

The document is a `Sweave` file – i.e., it is a mixture of `LaTeX` and `R` that is designed to be compiled into a report in pdf (or another format such as html). We have tested it using the `Knitr` package in `R` version 4.1.1 (2021-08-10). Readers wishing to see the underlying code should view the version with the `.Rnw` suffix, and look for code chunks starting with `<<`.

By default,

1.1 Background

The tracking experiment at the Great Belt site near Kerteminde (analyzed in SAMBAH Code File 2) involved acoustic tracking of wild-swimming porpoises; the detection or non-detection of these porpoises on adjacent CPODs was then used to construct a detection function for detectability of porpoises as a function of distance from a CPOD, as well as other explanatory variables such as time of day. This detection function was then used to estimate an effective detection area (EDA) at Kerteminde; this was then combined with playback data from Kerteminde and the SAMBAH stations to estimate the EDA at the SAMBAH stations.

However, since the trials at Kerteminde involved vocalizing animals, they estimate the probability of detection of an animal that is vocalizing, and so over-estimate the population-wide probability of detection and corresponding EDA. We need to adjust the EDA to account for the proportion of the population that is not vocalizing. More precisely, we want to estimate the proportion of animals at Kerteminde that passed by the sensors during the trial but did not vocalize – we define this as p_c , and we use it to reduce the size of the EDA estimated from the acoustic trial data as follows:

$$\hat{\nu}_{i,m,d} = \frac{\hat{\nu}_d^* \hat{\xi}_{i,m}}{\hat{\xi}^*} \times \hat{p}_c \quad (1)$$

Where

- $\hat{\nu}_d^*$ is the estimated EDA for porpoises in diel phase d estimated at the Kerteminde experimental site, using acoustic encounters with porpoises that were clicking;
- $\hat{\xi}^*$ is the estimated EDA for an artificial click at the Kerteminde experimental site;
- $\hat{\xi}_{i,m}$ is the predicted EDA for an artificial click at sampling location i and month m , estimated from the playback study in the SAMBAH area.

We estimate p_c as follows. A sample of data from porpoises (from nearby waters) fitted with acoustic recording tags were available, giving us times of clicks produced by those animals. We assumed click behaviour of these porpoises was representative of porpoises at Kerteminde. There were 36 encounters of porpoises at Kerteminde, with acoustic track durations ranging from 5 to 263 seconds (median 56, mean 64.1). For each of these encounter lengths, we used the tag data to determine the probability each tagged porpoise would vocalize at least once during that time period, and so be available to be tracked. For each tagged porpoise, we then took the mean of these probabilities (averaging over all 36 encounters) to estimate the mean probability of clicking at least once during an encounter. Lastly, to obtain the population average, we took a weighted mean across tagged animals, weighting by the number of seconds of data on each tag. This analysis therefore treats the tagged porpoise as the sample unit. More details are given in the remainder of this report, and also in the methods section of the paper.

2 ATag data

There were tag data from 6 porpoises available, with a total deployment time of 802.01 hours (Table 1). The data were rounded to the nearest second to facilitate processing. The acoustic recording tag was duty cycled, so that it was on between 10 and 45 minutes each hour (different tags had different duty cycle regimes); the total ATag on time over all tags was 162.27. In addition, it was necessary to discard data from when the porpoise was at $< 2\text{m}$ depth because interference from surface noise means it is not possible accurately to distinguish clicks from surface noise. Data from two depth sensors were available; we elected to use that from the Star-Oddi sensor because that was available for the entire deployment. Depth was recorded approximately every 3 seconds; we used linear interpolation between these measurements to estimate depth at the resolution of 1 second. Data from seconds where the animal was estimated to be at $< 2\text{m}$ depth were discarded, leaving 74.245 hours (i.e., 267281 seconds) of data. In this time, the total number of seconds where a click was detected on the tag was 102247, giving a mean proportion of click-positive seconds of 0.3825. This number is not useful for our purposes, because we need the average proportion of intervals that contain a click where the intervals we average over are the lengths of the encounters at Kerteminde, not just 1 second. We address this in the next following sections.

Animal	Start time	Stop time	Duration	w/ ATag	<2m depth	w/ clicks	p(click)
1	2010-05-19 20:07:22	2010-05-29 09:50:08	826966	137833	60082	38480	0.6405
2	2011-04-14 16:15:00	2011-04-16 18:23:00	180480	135480	41922	9935	0.2370
3	2011-05-06 17:25:15	2011-05-08 22:52:41	192446	29160	18198	11594	0.6371
4	2011-07-04 19:50:28	2011-07-07 05:43:41	208393	34800	22615	10155	0.4490
5	2011-07-15 18:52:30	2011-07-21 19:31:59	520769	86969	52313	18619	0.3559
6	2011-03-29 15:00:00	2011-04-09 17:09:56	958196	159930	72151	13464	0.1866
Total			2887250	584172	267281	102247	0.3825

Table 1: Summary of ATag data. Duration is the length of the tag deployment (in seconds), w/ ATag is the total period in which the ATag was recording (less than total duration because of duty cycling), $\geq 2\text{m}$ is the subset of this time at which the porpoise was estimated to be at greater than 2m depth, w/clicks is the number of click positive seconds. p(click) is the proportion of the seconds at which the animal was $\geq 2\text{m}$ that were click positive.

3 Estimation of probability of click at each encounter duration

Data from each porpoise was analyzed separately. As stated earlier, there were 36 encounters, ranging from 5 to 263 seconds in duration. For each of these encounter durations, the tag data was divided into chunks of this

Figure 1: Estimated probability (from a monotonic binary GAM) of at least 1 click-positive second per chunk as a function of the proportion of censored data (i.e., data where the porpoise is estimated to be $< 2m$). This example is for animal 1, and chunk duration 56 seconds (the median encounter length). The solid line is the fitted function; dashed lines show the 95%CI on the fit. The short vertical lines at top and bottom show click-positive chunks (at top) and click-negative chunks (at bottom) (note: position on the x-axis is jittered for clarity).

duration, and only chunks where the ATag was on for the entire duration were retained. Chunks where the porpoise was at an estimated depth $< 2m$ for the entire duration were also discarded. For those remaining, we calculated the proportion of chunks that contained one or more click-positive seconds.

3.1 Correction for depth $< 2m$ data

As would be expected, chunks with a greater proportion of seconds where the porpoise was at $< 2m$ depth had a lower probability of being click-positive (i.e., of having one or more click-positive seconds) – because clicks detected at depths $< 2m$ had previously been truncated (i.e., removed). Ideally we would have excluded all chunks containing any data from $< 2m$ but this would have removed too much data (and also possibly caused bias if click rates are very different at deeper depths); instead we elected to use an analysis to estimate the probability a chunk is click-positive for chunks with no truncated data. We used the R package `scam` to fit a logistic regression of click positive/not click positive seconds as a function of the proportion of the chunk $< 2m$ (i.e., truncated). Proportion $< 2m$ was modelled using a monotonic nonincreasing smooth – in other words, we assumed that the larger the proportion of the chunk containing $< 2m$ depths, the smaller the probability the chunk would contain a click. Examples, using the median chunk duration, are shown in Figure 1 (for the porpoise with the highest per-second probability of clicking) and Figure 2 (for the porpoise with the lowest per-second probability of clicking). We then used the fitted model to predict the probability of being click positive for 0 proportion of the chunk at $< 2m$ (i.e., the intercept in the above plots).

Figure 2: Same plot as previous figure, but for animal 6 (still with chunk duration 56 seconds), which showed the lowest per-second probability of clicking. Here, even after a 56 seconds with no click data censored, it is estimated that the probability of at least one click is $\hat{\mu}$.

Figure 3: Estimated probability of there being one or more click (y-axis) for a range of encounter durations in seconds (x-axis) and over 6 animals (solid lines). Note that the estimates have been smoothed for clarity. The encounter durations used in the analysis are indicated by short vertical lines along the x-axis.

3.2 Results

Estimates of probability of click for each encounter duration and for each animal are shown in Figure 3. The mean probability of a click, averaged across the 36 encounter durations are shown in Table 2.

Animal	p(click)	T	w
1	0.958	60082	0.225
2	0.671	41922	0.157
3	0.936	18198	0.068
4	0.941	22615	0.085
5	0.851	52313	0.196
6	0.708	72151	0.270

Table 2: Mean probability of click ($p(\text{click})$), averaged over the encounter durations; also shown (T) is the number of seconds in which the ATag was recording and the depth was $< 2\text{m}$ – this is the weight used in averaging over animals; the weight standardized so it sums to 1 is shown in the last column (w).

4 Estimation of p_c across encounters and porpoises

The final estimate of p_c is a weighted mean of the $p(\text{click})$ values shown in Table 2, weighted by the number of seconds of data used for each animal (shown as T in that table). This value is 0.8215.

We also estimated the variance of the weighted mean, using the method described by Cochran (1977; see also Gatz and Luther 1995). This value is 0.00316231.

5 Examination of diel pattern in click-positive seconds

At reviewers' request we did some additional analyses to examine whether there were any patterns in click behaviour with time of day. We focussed on diel phase, because that is how we divided our main analyses. We grouped the data according to the diel phase of each day for each tag. The table 3 shows the proportion of time on the tag records that is in each diel phase. On average over the 6 tags the proportion of time in dawn, day, dusk and night was 0.0364, 0.6452, 0.0386, 0.2798, respectively.

Table 4 shows the proportion of time spent at 2m or deeper by diel phase, and Table 5 shows the proportion of click-positive seconds while at these depths. These results are also shown graphically in Figure 4. Although each animal shows some differences between diel phases, particularly in the proportion of click-positive seconds, there are no consistent patterns apparent across the porpoises. Averaging the proportions of time at 2m or deeper across tags (without any sort of weighting for length of tag record) yields proportions by diel phase of 0.524, 0.516, 0.480, 0.498 and averaging the proportion of click-positive seconds gives 0.513, 0.397, 0.425, 0.457. There was, however, strong variation among animals, with proportion of time at depths of ≥ 2 m in the range 0.285, 0.647 and proportion of CPS in the range 0.217, 0.720.

Dawn	Day	Dusk	Night
0.041	0.696	0.038	0.225
0.027	0.610	0.028	0.335
0.030	0.627	0.045	0.298
0.054	0.667	0.055	0.224
0.039	0.712	0.040	0.209
0.027	0.559	0.027	0.387

Table 3: Proportion of time in each diel phase.

Dawn	Day	Dusk	Night
0.437	0.453	0.466	0.408
0.254	0.361	0.282	0.244
0.736	0.597	0.576	0.672
0.646	0.631	0.668	0.645
0.610	0.601	0.461	0.586
0.462	0.456	0.427	0.436

Table 4: Proportion of diel phase for each of the tagged porpoises spent at depths of 2m or deeper.

Dawn	Day	Dusk	Night
0.805	0.583	0.705	0.785
0.300	0.200	0.275	0.325
0.741	0.630	0.573	0.649
0.384	0.485	0.503	0.338
0.547	0.329	0.305	0.422
0.300	0.154	0.189	0.225

Table 5: Proportion of click-positive seconds for each of the tagged porpoises while at depths of 2m or deeper.

We also summarized the data by hour of the day, and this is shown in Figure 5.

References

- Cochran, W. G. Sampling Techniques, 3rd Edition. 3rd edn, (Wiley, 1977).
- Gatz, D. F. and Luther, S. The standard error of a weighted mean concentration-I. Bootstrapping vs other methods,. Atmospheric Environment 29, 1185-1193 (1995).

Figure 4: Exploratory analysis of diel patterns in proportion of time spent at 2m or deeper and proportion of click-positive seconds while at these depths (and while the tags were recording).

Figure 5: Proportion of click-positive seconds while at 2m or deeper (and while the tags were recording) by hour of the day.